

THE CONTENT OF PREPARING STUDENTS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY IN THE PROCESS OF INDIVIDUAL EDUCATION

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Abstract. *There is a need to improve the quality of personnel by increasing the efficiency of education, ensuring that students receive an excellent and high-quality education in the process of training future personnel, creating sufficient conditions for them, and taking into account individual characteristics and student capabilities. It is known that for various objective and subjective reasons, some students quite often drop out of school. The article provides comments on individual education programs (IEP), which allow this category of students to successfully complete their studies.*

Keywords: *individual educational program (IEP), training requirements, individual training conditions, individual training opportunities, academic leave, reinstatement, final certification, control.*

Huge democratic reforms implemented in our country serve to change the attitude of each of the young people living in our country to live happily, seek education, learn a profession, and look at life in a new way.

In the course of the reforms, ample opportunities are being created for the all-round development of the individual and for the effective education of young people.

1. In modern society, the level of development of one or another country is determined not only by its technical condition, but also by the professional competence of specialists trained in higher education institutions. In today's conditions, it is an important direction to optimize the training of specialists, the maximum satisfaction of the educational needs of individuals and society, and the differentiation of professional training in the higher education system.

The main characteristic of continuous professional training is to follow the principle of follow-up, to rely on traditions in achieving educational goals. The analysis of the activities of teachers being trained in higher education institutions shows that they have the ability to form professional competence related to their subject and the education of the mature generation and to consistently apply them in their future professional activities. requires that

Ensuring the development and prospects of our country is connected with major changes in the economic, social, political and cultural spheres.

2. In the present period, every member of the society, which is rapidly developing in all directions, has an increasing level of knowledge, scientific and innovative thinking and effective use of complex man-made devices in production. This, in turn, is related to the deep knowledge of the population. That is why it is necessary for us to expand the opportunities for our young people, who are directed to a certain profession in all sectors and branches of our economy, to get deep knowledge at every stage of education.

Individual education programs (IEP) is a method of mastering a curriculum that is tailored to the student's educational needs. It does not depend on the form of study: a student can go to it regardless of whether he studies in full-time or part-time departments. A student studying according to an individual plan can make his own schedule of tests and exams and freely choose the method of completing assignments.

It is known that the educational process at the university is regulated by the curriculum. Individual education programs (IEP) is a document that defines the subjects, courses, modules and practices to be completed in the course of training in a specialty. It is developed by the teachers of the department on the basis of the State Education Standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan and is approved by the Dean or Rector by the orders of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation.

The student can find out from the curriculum which subjects will be taught in the semester, how many hours are allocated to study each subject, in what format they plan to test student knowledge - a test or an exam.

If a student cannot attend classes with others for any reason, he has the right to switch to an individual study plan. When transferring to IEP, the student determines the format in which he will study each subject by discussing with the administration and teachers. The teacher decides how to assess the student's knowledge: assigns essays or other written tasks, conducts regular exams, or devises other ways to monitor the state of mastery. Often, teachers send lecture notes and reference lists, and the student submits completed seminar and practical assignments within an agreed upon time frame.

Individual education programs (IEP) does not always include a distance learning format. It all depends on the capabilities of the university and the format agreed upon by the teachers. Formats may vary from university to university - for example, one university may allow a student to go fully online, while another may not because they lack the technical resources to do so.

Individual education programs (IEP) is not a panacea for the student, it does not give the student the opportunity to completely abandon the things he does not like. The student will be required to pass tests and exams together with the students he is studying or other groups.

Each student has the right to study according to an individual plan, but each university determines the conditions and procedures for transferring students to IEP. How the transfer process works should be defined in the regulation on personnel training on Individual education programs (IEP) and published on the official website of the educational institution.

Almost all universities have similar reasons for applying for an individual plan.

1. Transfer to another educational program or reinstatement after academic leave.

In such cases, an academic difference may appear - a list of subjects that the student did not study on time for any reason. Individual education programs (IEP) allows the student to complete them, pass the exams and continue his studies.

2. Intensive learning. The duration of the educational program can be shortened in two cases:

1. If the student plans to complete the program faster than the established schedule.
2. If the student previously mastered these subjects in college or additional courses.

Generally, in order to transfer, a student must have completed 3 credits and be able to explain their motivation in their application.

3. If he is currently working in the specialty he wants to acquire in the future. For example, if a student is a senior in the Faculty of Education and works at a school, the student may be considered a practicum and attend classes on an individual schedule.

4. If the student has health problems. Illnesses that prevent normal studies - for example, if the student is in the hospital for a long time and cannot attend the university regularly.

5. Personal achievements and other special occasions. In this case, universities have the right to determine their own reasons for transfer.

6. Family conditions. When close relatives are seriously ill or when there is a need to take care of children under three years of age. However, it should be taken into account that the requirement is still to study and pass exams, so in such cases it is better to take an academic leave.

How is training organized on the basis of Individual education programs (IEP)?

Most of the process is regulated by the local regulations of the universities. A student studying according to an individual plan must study all the subjects included in your curriculum.

The size of the curriculum is the number of academic hours allocated to study the subject, that is, it is measured in credit units. If teaching is not accelerated, the credit units for each subject will remain the same at Individual education programs (IEP) only the format of mastering the program will change: the number of lecture hours will decrease, and the time for independent mastering of the material will increase. will appear. Subjects are studied in the same order.

The implementation of the program is usually monitored by the dean based on the results of the interim and final attestation.

The university may consider certain subjects as completed if the student has prior knowledge of the relevant specialty. For this, the student must confirm his existing knowledge by passing an exam to a special commission or faculty dean.

Typically, an individual plan does not limit student attendance. For example, a student can participate in training in specialized subjects and study general subjects independently. Tests and exams can be taken individually or in a group.

Switching to an individual study plan allows the student to make the study process at the university more flexible and attend only the necessary classes, as well as create his own schedule of tests and exams. Learning does not stop, but in some cases it is enough to send completed assignments to the teacher on time to pass the course.

The list of reasons for transfer is determined by the university. In order to transfer, the student must justify why he/she cannot attend classes with other students. If the university refuses to transfer to the Individual education programs (IEP) the problem can be addressed to the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

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